

Paraplegia Following Spinal-Epidural Anesthesia in Lumbar Canal Stenosis: A Case Report

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Abstract:

Background: Paraplegia following neuroaxial block is one of the rare complication a severe form of cauda equina syndrome. Reporting such rare cases is essential for continuing medical education. We are presenting a case report of post epidural complete paraplegia in a patient with severe spinal canal stenosis.

Case presentation: A 51-year-old female presented to our clinic on post operative day 2 with complete paraplegia following a bilateral total knee replacement surgery under spinal epidural anesthesia done elsewhere in the city. Epidural catheter was removed on POD 1 till then two top-ups were given and anticoagulants (Inj. enoxaparin 40mg sc once a day) were started on postoperative day 1, while mechanical anticoagulation was started immediately in post operative period. Patient was started on steroids and when no recovery could be documented L1 to L5 central decompression was performed on POD 9. Recovery was not significant.

Conclusion: Manifestations of cauda equina syndrome might get accentuated to varying severity following a neuroaxial blockade in a patient with already compromised canal. Preanesthetic identification of such cases should be considered, and appropriate anaesthetic precautions should be undertaken, prompt identification and appropriate management of these complications should be considered for fruitful outcome.

Abbreviations: POD, post operative day; CES, cauda equina syndrome; NA, neuraxial anesthesia DVT, deep vein thrombosis MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; TKR, total knee replacement; LCS, lumbar canal stenosis.

Keywords: Paraplegia, Cauda Equina Syndrome, Neuraxial Anesthesia, Spinal Canal Stenosis, Epidural Anesthesia, Postoperative Complications.

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Introduction

Epidural anesthesia are commonly used in today's anesthetic practice, and complications are rare. Damage to the conus medullaris and cauda equina has been reported in the literature, certainly with medicolegal implications. The occurrence of neurologic complications after neuraxial anesthesia (NA) is very rare—between 1–1000/1–100,000.[1] Cauda equine syndrome (CES) is the second most frequent neurological complication of neuraxial blockades after spinal hematoma More than two-thirds of CES can result in permanent neurological deficits.[2]

Pre-existing spinal stenosis has been reported to be a risk factor of neurological complications after epidural anesthesia.[3] Although there is no previous imaging available as solid proof, Neurologic complications may be more severe in the presence of spinal stenosis.

Case report

A 51-year-old female presented to spine outpatient department on postop day 2 of her bilateral total knee replacement surgery with complete paraplegia

where combined block was used for surgery done elsewhere in the city.

Preoperative history of severe bilateral knee pain and chronic low back pain was retrieved from patient. There was no other significant neurological history. There is history of multiple punctures during the attempt for block. 2 top up were given to patient for pain management in postoperative period, epidural catheter was removed after 24 hours of surgery. Inj. Enoxaparin 40mg sc once a day) were started on POD 1, 12 hours after removing epidural, along with mechanical anticoagulation. Patient gives history of weakness of lower extremities following surgery which didn't recovered at any point of time since then. patient didn't passed stools since then and foley's catheter was applied preoperatively. Documentation showed use of 23-gauge epidural needle and injection of hyperbaric bupivacaine with glucose into epidural space

Two top up were given for pain management each consisting of 10 ml solution of fentanyl.

MRI was performed on postoperative day 2 and it showed multiple large central disc prolapse at all levels from L1 to S1, along with ligamentum flavum

hypertrophy and facet arthropathy. Canal diameter at L1-L2 was 4.19 mm, at L2-L3 Level-4.4 mm, at L3-L4 level-3.95 mm, at L4-L5 level-3.29 mm and at L5-S1-6.02 mm.(figure 3)

Neurological examination on arrival showed grade 0 power with complete sensory loss (sensory level L2), absent deep tendon reflexes and plantar equivocal, saddle anesthesia and absent bladder and bowel sensation.

Patient was started on Tab pregabalin 75 mg twice daily and Inj dexamethasone four times a day and when no recovery could be documented L1 to L5 central decompression was performed. (POD 9 of total knee replacement.)

Patient only recovered partially following it at 6 months follow up without return of bladder and bowel control but improvement of saddle anaesthesia and no improvement of power.

Figure 1: Preoperative skin condition suggesting multiple attempts for block.

Discussion

Permanent neurological injury in form of cauda equine syndrome following epidural analgesia is extremely rare complication with a few case reports published worldwide and specifically a case of paraplegia. To the best of our knowledge, this is a unique case of complete paraplegia following epidural anesthesia.

The possible mechanism of this type of complication can include combination of multiple factors that can

cause trauma, compression, ischemia and neurotoxicity. possible factors that should be considered are: trauma to the nerve roots at the time of needle insertion, the type and volume of local anesthetic injected, the dose and concentration of the drug and the duration of exposure, and, finally, the injection of the epidural dose of local anesthetic intrathecally or subdurally. Contaminants and unintentional injection of drugs not intended for spinal or epidural use must always be included in the differential diagnosis of the etiology of CES. One or more of these factors alone or in combination may lead to CES. In lumbar canal stenosis patients multiple attempts which are usually required for block can cause direct damage to nerve roots, as nerve roots are already very crowded in these patients, while the normal amount of injected local anesthetic can increase the canal pressure tremendously and can further damage nerve roots. Baricity, concentration, and duration and maldistribution of the local anesthetic appear to be important considerations in the development of neurotoxicity.[4,5,6]

Epidural hematoma, a well known complication of epidural block can be a potential threat for spinal cord compression both during the procedure and especially when catheter is removed in a patient on anticoagulants (for DVT prophylaxis), which however was not seen in our patients MRI.[7]

Auroy et al.[8] in a prospective trial with 30,413 patients came through 6 neurological complications of which 5 were reversible radiculopathies and 1 patient of paraplegia, cause of which they attributed was prolonged intraoperative hypotension leading to spinal cord ischemia. There was no case of cauda equina in the studies by Horlocker et al.[9] and Dahlgren and Tornebrandt[10]. these studies denotes that CES is a rare complication.

Other case reports worldwide shows incidences of CES post NA. Kubina et al.[4] reported 2 cases of CES post spinal anaesthesia.They observed patchy and failed blocks due to disc prolapse and concluded these patterns should alert anaesthesiologist for potential neurological complications.

Merino-Urrutia et al. [11] in a single shot spinal block for Bartholin abscess removal noticed CES. They also found increased gadolinium accumulation in neural sheaths and attributed needle trauma and neurotoxic effects of bupivacaine for CES presentation. They also noticed clinical improvement with conservative management.

Figure 2: MRI of patient showing severe canal stenosis.

Shields et al.[12] reported 2 cases of CES. In first case epidural block in adhesive arachnoiditis was considered as this patient had history of L4 L5 laminectomy and fusion and in second case direct injection into the cord/conus likely contributed to neurological injury as anesthesiologist placed needle at L1-L2 level. Incorrect determination of the lumbar interspace level was also a causative factor in case reports by Melloni et al.[13] and Hamandi et al.[14].

Stambough et al.[15] presented a case report of a patient with CES post TKR with high grade LCS at L3-L4 level. Prolonged catheter placement and local medication was considered causative factor. Only partial recovery could be achieved after bilateral foraminotomy and partial medial facetectomy.

This patient had canal stenosis and was relatively asymptomatic before surgery. Multiple pathologies including lumbar canal stenosis at all levels from L1 to S1, along with ligamentum flavum hypertrophy and facet arthropathy noticed on MRI. Epidural dose of anaesthetic agent could have been injected into intrathecal space or sub arachnoid space as epidural space was narrow and was displaced dorsally. These large doses of anesthetic agent could've caused potential neurotoxicity and even arachnoiditis. Epidural catheter which occupies epidural space was retained for 24 hours in our patient, this itself could've contribute to pressure effect in such patients. Large volume of epidural anaesthetic agents could've created large pressure in an already

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compromised canal leading to space occupying effects. All these possible causes can be included in explanation of such a case.

Declaration of patient consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent forms. In the form the patient has given his/her consent for his/her images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patients understand that their names and initials will not be published, and due efforts will be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Conclusion

Lumbar canal stenosis can increase the risk of cord compression and damage during a neuroaxial blockade, which can vary in severity. The explanation for this complication is uncertain but could be due to a combination of needle trauma or due to the neurotoxic properties of Bupivacaine or large volume of local anesthetic causing severe compression in already compromised canal. Preanesthetic identification of such cases should be considered, and prompt identification and appropriate management of these complications should be considered for fruitful outcome.

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